

The Role of Paywalls in Online Information-Seeking Behavior: A Review of Literature

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ABSTRACT

This poster presents the first phase of a study into the effect of paywalls on the online information-seeking behavior of Canadian midwives. Using a narrative review approach, the authors have reviewed and synthesized the literature on the effect of paywalls on information-seeking behavior. Important questions were raised about institutions and associations paying for access on behalf of their members. In addition, suggestions are made on the gaps that need to be filled, such as (a) a need to examine how the different types of paywall configurations affect online information-seeking behavior; (b) a need for more interviews and surveys to better understand the phenomenon; and (c) a need to examine the role paywalls play in aspects of online information-seeking behavior other than the number of visits, downloads and article view times.

KEYWORDS

Online information-seeking behavior, Paywalls, Perceived Value, Source Selection.

INTRODUCTION

As the ever-expanding number of documents online reaches the billions, with no centralized structure to ensure quality, finding the best information continues to become more and more difficult. A common challenge in the process of searching for information online is the phenomenon of hitting paywalls. Because it is practically impossible for libraries and associations to provide access to all information sources on the Internet, even information seekers who have access through their subscriptions still hit paywalls sometimes. Paywalls serve as a system for mediating access to content by distinguishing between users who have paid for the access and those who have not. They are cited as a major barrier to access of information (Barnes et al., 2020; Steel & Adams, 2011) and have been criticized by the open access movement (Day et al., 2020; James, 2020), although open access has its own flaws (Frank et al., 2022).

As a first step to examining how paywalls affect the online information-seeking behavior of Canadian midwives in their work-related context, this study sought to answer the question: what is known about how paywalls affect online information-seeking behavior? Reviews available on paywalls typically examined the trends in paywall configurations and implementations (Carson, 2015; Rußell et al., 2020). This poster presents the findings from a narrative review of the literature.

METHODS

Based on the definition of information-seeking behavior by Wilson (2000 p. 49), we refer to online information-seeking behavior as all the activities involved in purposive seeking for information on the Internet to satisfy some need, including source evaluation and selection. The LISA and LISTA databases accessed through the McGill University database were searched. Additional references were identified from bibliographic information. Search terms included: paywalls, pay-per-view, pay-per-use, pay-per-period, and information-seeking behavior. Articles from 2000-2022 discussing paywalls and information-seeking behavior were selected for review. In total, 83 articles were reviewed. Notetaking focused on how paywalls affect information-seeking.

FINDINGS

Very few studies were identified which focused on the impact of paywalls on online information-seeking behavior (e.g., Gershenson et al., 2020; Nicholas et al., 2003; Raban et al., 2019; Raban & Mazor, 2013). Most of the studies that examined the impact of paywalls studied news media (e.g., Chae & Schweidel, 2022; Chiou & Tucker, 2013; Cook & Attari, 2012). Others reported paywalls as a barrier to online information-seeking although their focus was not on studying paywalls (e.g., Barnes et al., 2020; Kesselman, 2010; Steel & Adams, 2011). Studies most frequently used experiments, log analysis, or surveys as methods, and focused on examining statistics like the number of visits, article view times, and number of downloads. The populations studied were students, academics, and the public. Three forms of paywalls were identified: (1) donation requests, like on Wikipedia; (2) soft access restrictions, which allow at least some free content, and (3) hard access restrictions (pay-per-view or pay-per-period) which restrict access to content by offering only paid content (Rußell et al., 2020).

A series of experimental studies mimicking paywall systems with students in online information-seeking environments established that they perceived the value of information items to be high when they were required to pay for access, they selected more of such sources (critically) for decision making, and they were willing to pay for access (Raban et al., 2019; Raban & Mazor, 2013; Raban & Rafaeli, 2006). These findings buttress the propositions

Mid-Year Conference of the Association for Information Science & Technology | April 11-13, 2023, Virtual Event. Author(s) retain copyright, but ASIS&T receives an exclusive publication license.

of key models and experiments from consumer behavior literature (Brock, 1968, p. 44; Lynn, 1991; Plassmann et al., 2008).

Other studies found negative impacts of paywalls, with paywalls reported as a major barrier to the access of information sources among professionals (Barnes et al., 2020; Gershenson et al., 2020; Steel & Adams, 2011). Gershenson et al. (2020) found that making journals open access increased article downloads in those journals by 55% to 95% per month. In the context of news sites, Chiou and Tucker (2013) found a 51% drop in visits after the introduction of a paywall. Print journals who offered their subscribers a deal to keep paying the same amount they were paying for print copies to get full access to content online had more journal use compared to non-deal subscribers (Nicholas et al., 2003).

DISCUSSION

There appear to be contradictory findings on the effect of paywalls on information-seeking behavior. Paywalls seemed to affect how students in a lab situation perceived the value of information sources, and this perceived value was a primary factor that influenced their information-seeking behavior. However, at the same time paywalls were perceived as a barrier to information in other studies. Possible reasons for this contradiction are the differences in the methods used, the type of information/source, the population, the purpose for seeking information, and income availability. More studies on this subject will be needed to understand this contradiction and make a generalized conclusion.

The findings from this literature review raise several questions and issues for future consideration and research. First, given that allowing information seekers to directly pay for access affects their perception of value and ultimately their use of information sources, it is worth it for libraries and associations to subscribe on behalf of information seekers, or it is better to give them a form of financial support to pay on their own? It appears that paying on behalf of everybody is cost effective, but if it becomes necessary, could institutions instead negotiate a discount for their members? Making this decision will also depend on whether the information seekers do their searching directly or get the information they need from an information professional. Although some institutions have information professionals who conduct searches on behalf of members, most of the time, individuals may end up doing their own searches for information. Second, given the same reasons as earlier, should open access be encouraged or premium access?

Another point worth considering is how the different types of paywall configurations affect online information-seeking behavior. In the experiment of Raban et al. (2019), participants were willing to donate money after getting access to free sources. This suggests that the donation request form of paywall may be a good option, but this is not conclusive. Further studies, more likely using the experimental method, may be useful to examine how the different types of paywall configuration affect online information-seeking behavior. Finally, information-seeking behavior is much more than the number of visits, article view times, and number of downloads. There is therefore the need to understand how paywalls affect online information-seeking behavior in totality: browsing, source evaluation, selection, extraction, and use.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This review has identified the main trends and themes from the literature on the effect of paywalls on information-seeking behavior. We know from this literature that different kinds of paywall configurations exist, but we do not have enough findings on how each of these configurations affects information-seeking behavior. There also appears to be a contradiction between the effect of paywalls on information-seeking behavior observed in experimental studies and those that did log analysis or surveys. One of the interesting outcomes of this review is the question as to whether it is worth paying for access on behalf of information seekers, given the unseen benefits of individuals directly paying for access. Studies using interview and survey methods of data collection are needed to better understand how paywalls affect online information-seeking. Future studies can also examine the role paywalls play in other aspects of information-seeking behavior other than demand for content, article view times and the number of downloads. To further contribute to this literature, the authors will investigate some of these areas in more depth with Canadian midwives, ultimately to examine how paywalls are affecting their evidence-based health practices.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their profound gratitude to the supervisory committee: Dr. Rebekah Wilson, Dr. Max Evans, and the research group of Dr. Joan Bartlett at McGill SIS; and the ASIS&T reviewers for their constructive feedback.

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